

Trisecting an Arbitrary Acute Angle with Euclidean Tools and Origami Inspiration

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Trisecting an arbitrary acute angle using only a compass and straightedge has long been shown to be impossible¹. Angle trisection has, however, been accomplished using origami procedures. Methods for achieving a good estimate of angle trisection with Euclidean tools and origami insight are presented. Bisections or any other step easily done with a compass and a straight edge are not discussed in detail.

Method A

Create a diagram, as shown in Figure 1, consisting of two parallel horizontal lines on an x-y coordinate plane, where the segments **AB = BC = DE = EF**.

Figure 1

Draw a line from point **A** to point **G** forming $\angle FAG$, which is $\angle \theta$ that is to be trisected. The intersection of **AG** with **CD** establishes point **H**. Using only a compass and straightedge, construct a segment from **H** to a point **I** on **BE** with the length of **HI** equal to **AC**. With a straight edge, construct the segment **AI**. Bisect $\angle IAH$ forming segment **AL**.

$\angle FAL$ is an estimate of $\frac{2}{3} \angle \theta$.

It remains to bisect $\angle FAL$ (easily done with a compass and straight edge), resulting in a line that is an estimate of $\frac{1}{3} \angle \theta$, completing the approximation for the trisection of $\angle \theta$.

Method B

Trisecting the arbitrary acute $\angle\theta$ with origami has been effectively demonstrated in Numberphile². Method B is, in effect, an effort to mimic the origami method for trisecting an arbitrary acute angle. The origami procedure presented in Numberphile creates a trapezoid consisting of two equal legs and parallel top and bottom bases as shown in Figure 2. It is done by folding the point **A** to the line **BE** and folding the point **C** to the line representing $\angle\theta$. These folds are done simultaneously while maintaining the length **AC**. This results in a crease in the paper from **J** to **K**. The crease crosses **BE** at point **L**. $\angle\text{FAL}$ is an exact measure of $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$ and is illustrated by the trapezoid shown in Figure 2.

Similar in construction to the procedure presented in Method A, create a diagram, consisting of two parallel horizontal lines on an x-y coordinate plane, where the segments **AB = BC = DE = EF**. This method (shown in Figure 2) represents an effort to mimic the origami technique with Euclidean tools. Draw a line from point **A** to point **G** forming $\angle\text{FAG}$, which equals $\angle\theta$ that is to be trisected. The intersection of **AG** with **CD** establishes point **H**. Construct a segment from **H** to a point **I** on **BE** with the length of **HI** equal to **AC**. Create a segment **AM** on **AG** with the length **AI**. Find the midpoint **J** of **CM** and the midpoint **K** of **AI**. Construct a segment **JK**. **JK** intersects **BE** at the point **L**. Construct a segment **AN** that intersects **BE** at point **L**.

$\angle\text{FAN}$ is an estimate of $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$.

If the arbitrary $\angle\theta$ is equal to 45° or 90° , $\angle\text{FAN}$ is an exact measure of $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$. For an arbitrary $\angle\theta$ that is unequal to 45° or 90° , **MI** \neq **AC** and the trapezoid created will not exhibit the mirror image about **JK** that is formed with the origami technique. **MI** \neq **AC** contributes to the error in estimating $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$.

As in Method A, it remains to bisect $\angle\text{FAN}$, resulting in a line that is an estimate of $\frac{1}{3}\angle\theta$, completing the approximation for the trisection of $\angle\theta$.

Figure 2

Method Comparison

Using geometry³ and charting⁴ software, an error evaluation was performed for the two Methods discussed above and the results are shown in Figure 3. Error measurements of estimates of $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$ with 5-degree increments of $\angle\theta$ were done and trend lines are indicated.

Figure 3

Method A exhibits less error in the estimate of $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$ than Method B. Both methods exhibit maximum error in the vicinity of $\theta = 20^\circ$ and $\theta = 70^\circ$ and both methods result in exact measures of $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$ when θ equals 45° or 90° . Error in estimating $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$ approaches zero as θ approaches zero. As θ approaches zero, physical measurement difficulty with the use of a compass and straight edge as well as origami is evident.

Conclusion

Method A exhibits much less error in estimating $\frac{2}{3}\angle\theta$ than method B and is an easy method for approximating the trisection of the arbitrary acute angle θ .

1. Wantzel, L. (1837). "Recherches sur les moyens de reconnaître si un Problème de Géométrie peut se résoudre avec la règle et le compas" (Investigations into means of knowing if a problem of geometry can be solved with a straightedge and compass) *Journal de Mathématiques Pures et Appliquées*
2. <https://www.numberphile.com/videos/how-to-trisect-an-angle-with-origami?rq=origami>
3. GeoGebra geometry software
4. Microsoft Excel